

DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT WORK COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS OF “TEMURBEKLAR MAKTABI” BY MEANS OF ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

Jumayev J.A.

Independent researcher of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14212293>

Abstract. This article discusses about the development of independent work competencies of the students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” with the help of electronic educational resources, as well as information about the types, possibilities, and development of electronic educational resources.

Keywords: “Temurbeklar maktabi”, competence, e-learning resource, website, component.

It was concluded that in creating electronic educational resources, it is important to develop a set of requirements for their quality and to comply with them. Therefore, the process of creating electronic educational resources must meet technical, didactic, psychological, methodical, aesthetic, functional and ergonomic requirements.

One of the important advantages of electronic educational resources is a sharp increase in visibility of the educational process organized using it. E-learning resources have a sufficient number of possibilities that allow to increase the visibility of the educational process.

The main purpose of using electronic educational resources is to implement an individual approach to each student and to develop independent work skills in students.

In the forms of use of electronic learning resources created from the proposed general education subjects (see Figure 1.1), electronic learning resources will be located on disks and on the Internet. They are open and closed both on disks and on the Internet.

Within the framework of the study, special importance is attached to the structure of electronic educational resources aimed at teaching subjects, and a number of its components are listed: topic, slide, audio concept, exercises, homework, crossword, tests on the topic, etc.

Figure 1.1. Forms of using electronic educational resources

Closed e-learning resources are subjects in a class of general education subjects in a closed state, that is, there is a strict requirement to study the subjects in the given sequence, not the optional subject, but to deal with the subject. In this, topics are studied sequentially, that is, students, those interested in the related subject, and users engaged in it can master one topic, then move on to the next topic, and so on.

A model of developing independent work competencies of students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” by means of electronic educational resources was developed. The military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi”, developed during the research, includes all the components of the process of the model process of developing independent work competencies of the students of the military academic lyceum through electronic educational resources.

Targeted component: development of independent work competencies of students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” by means of electronic educational resources.

Content component: use of electronic educational resources consisting of multimedia and interactive elements in order to ensure the content of general education subjects, didactic materials, demonstrability in lessons, extracurricular activities, independent education.

Technological component: forms, methods, tools.

Outcome component: assessment criteria and levels and final outcomes are presented.

The model of development of independent work competencies of students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” by means of electronic educational resources was improved based on the following:

- means of electronic educational resources, scientific researches on the development of independent work competences of students by means of electronic educational resources, including experimental studies, set of solutions to the required tasks;

- development of independent work competencies of the students of military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” by means of electronic educational resources according to the principles of forming a dynamic and open model of educational results, as well as a model of the educational process flexible to continuously changing goals;

- development of ways of forming the educational independence of the student, who is ready to actively and rationally use electronic educational resources for independent study and development;

- creating a compensatory (sustainability) model of the educational process based on the requirements for the content of education and upbringing in the conditions of digitization and the characteristics of the digital generation;

- providing a flexible and pedagogically acceptable balance in the organization of independent education and individualization of the educational process in electronic educational resources;

- Provision of pedagogical conditions for continuous use of didactic possibilities of new and constantly improving electronic technologies by students of military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi”;

- Implementation of unique ways of using electronic educational resources to achieve the development of independent work competence of students of military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” and increase the efficiency of the educational process.

The model of development of independent work competences of students of military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” with the help of electronic educational resources helps to prioritize students' demand, aspiration, mobility aimed at increasing their practical performance, and to increase the student's independent work competence.

The following goals and objectives were defined in the development and improvement of this model.

The main goal:

“Temurbeklar maktabi” consists in describing the methodology of developing the independent work competencies of students of the military academic lyceum by means of electronic educational resources.

Specific goals:

-the special goal is to provide students with the necessary knowledge and skills to increase their independent work competence through electronic learning resources.

-teaching students how to work independently and use information on the electronic platform.

Duties:

- explaining to the students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” the benefits of independent work on themselves and the use of electronic educational resources by means of electronic educational resources;

-providing information on the history and modern trends of the development of independent work competences to the students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” by means of electronic educational resources;

-teaching the students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” to use electronic platforms created for independent work by means of electronic educational resources;

-creating a resource to provide educational methodological support and materials;

-monitoring the achievements of students of military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” in the process of independent work with the help of electronic educational resources;

-analyzing the effectiveness of educational resources in the educational process for students of military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” for independent work by means of electronic educational resources.

In research, the concepts of "systematic" and "continuity" are studied in relation to each other [1].

“Temurbeklar maktabi” in relation to the process of preparation for independent work of students of the military academic lyceum requires, on the one hand, the connection of the school as the main form of training, and on the other hand, requires interdependence of the content, forms, methods and means.

“Temurbeklar maktabi” was based on systematic and active approaches in the development of independent work competence of students of military academic lyceum through electronic education.

It is important to use a *systematic approach* in solving the problems of independent work of students with the help of electronic learning resources. The systematic approach implies the analysis of all factors affecting the pedagogical phenomenon as a studied system, aimed at ensuring the optimal functioning of the pedagogical systems included in the object of pedagogical influence of the subject of activity [2].

One of the most important research methods in modern scientific knowledge is the systematic approach. It is based on the rule that it is necessary to comprehensively study the phenomena and processes studied in science. Analyzing the teaching process from the point of view of a systematic approach, it can be noted that at the system level it functions as two subsystems, two sets of determinants: the internal and external related to the activities of educators (teachers). Systematic analysis of the teaching process allows studying consistency in the teaching process from these aspects. Attempts to take a systematic approach to the study of consistency in teaching have been in pedagogy for a long time [3].

Taking a systemic approach as a basis for researching the phenomenon of consistency, it can be noted that consistency at the system level works as a set of two subsystems: internal, expressed in the learning activities of students, and related to the activities of educator, at different stages of the external continuous education system [4].

In the study, the students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” were instructed to use educational platforms and technological tools based on a systematic approach, and the skills of working on the electronic platform were improved.

The study was based on an active approach to the development of independent work competence of the students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” by means of electronic educational resources.

An active approach to education was shown by N.F.Talizina [5] and others, that educational activity is not only a way of mastering the content of education and the development of the learner, the transfer of certain information to the student, but also it is carried out in the course of personal active activity. It is this situation that forms the psychological basis of an active approach to education, and has a great influence on the development of modern educational methods, and serves as a foundation for pedagogical technologies. According to N.F.Talizina [5], the active approach to learning has put the issue of the ratio of knowledge, skills and abilities of the student and the problem of their development during their educational activities into a new perspective. Knowledge is acquired during activity and is manifested only during activity, behind skills and competences there are always behavioral actions with a certain description [5]. According to O.B.Epishcheva [6] and others, the active approach helps to estimate the unity of important principle, theory and practice in pedagogy.

In the activity approach, the components of the person and the activity are studied in close connection with each other. An active approach represents certain intellectual and logical thinking activities, as well as practical activity methods. The active approach was considered necessary to improve the development of the competence of independent work of the students of “Temurbeklar maktabi” with the help of electronic educational resources, to ensure the activity of the subjects in the pedagogical processes and to motivate the subjects to perform the tasks set according to the specific goals.

An active approach is important in the development of independent work competence of students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” by means of electronic educational resources.

By using these methods in the educational process, the students of the military academic lyceum “Temurbeklar maktabi” will develop their skills of independent work on the electronic platform, while increasing the educational process, making it interesting, understandable and

interactive, as well as developing mastery and creative thinking. As a result, students develop independent thinking skills while learning to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

REFERENCES

1. Ибрагимова Е.М. Непрерывная допрофессиональная и профессиональная педагогическая подготовка учителя: монография /Е.М. Ибрагимова. -Казань: Казанский педуниверстет, 1999. -212с.
2. Слепцова, Ирина Федоровна Формирование готовности будущих воспитателей к взаимодействию с детьми дошкольного возраста в процессе профессиональной подготовки: диссертация ... кандидата педагогических наук : 13.00.08 Москва 2007
3. Батаршев А.В. Педагогическая система преемственности обучения в общеобразовательной и профессиональной школе /А.В. Батаршев. - С.-Петербург: Институт профтехобразования РАО, 1996. - 90с.
4. Yuldasheva F.T. Izchillik asosida talabalarning kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish. Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya. Toshkent – 2023. 139 b.
5. Талызина Н. Ф. Педагогическая психология: Учеб. пособие для студ. сред. пед. учеб. заведений. - М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 1998. - 288 с. ISBN 5-7695-0183-9
6. Епишева О.Б. Деятельностный подход как теоретическая основа проектирования методической системы обучения математике. Дисс....д- ра пед. наук. М, 1999.-410 с.